

Radio-Anatomical Study of the Patella with Special Reference to Patellar Height

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Abstract:

Patellar height is one of the important static factors for maintenance of patellar stability. Several radiological indices have been used to measure the height of the patella of which 'Insall-Salvati index' is the most frequently studied method so far. Aims and Objectives: To measure patellar height by 'Insall-Salvati ratio' from MRI and to evaluate different physiological factors, e.g., age, sex, side etc affecting 'Insall-Salvati ratio'. Materials and Methods: After taking approval from institutional ethical committee, the study was conducted in the KPC Medical College and Hospital over 1 year period of time. Detailed history was taken from 93 patients admitted in the Department of Orthopaedics in whom examinations of both the lower limbs were possible irrespective of their chief complaints and clinical features. 186 knee joints, i.e., both knee joints of all the 93 patients were subjected to radiological investigation (MRI). The data obtained by the examination was analysed to see variation of Patellar Height by 'Insall-Salvati ratio' with sex, age and laterality and also to see the distribution of patients with respect of knee pain. Results: The clinical method which was newly attempted in this study, showed no statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) from their radiological one both on the right and left sides. The scenario was similar for both the age groups and for male as well as female patients. Conclusion: The clinical method could not yield any significant difference from radiological method within subjects of comparable age groups on either side in either sex.

Keywords: Patella, Insall-Salvati ratio, MRI.

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Introduction

The patella is a sesamoid bone integrated into the extensor apparatus between the quadriceps tendon and the ligamentum patellae (patellar ligament). Role of patellar height in knee joint biomechanics has great significance especially in the sports medicine, dislocation of patella and patella-femoral pain syndrome.

Patellar height is one of the important static factors for maintenance of patellar stability. Several radiological indices have been used to measure the height of the patella of which 'Insall-Salvati index' is the most frequently studied method so far.

Insall and Salvati in 1971 reviewed 114 radiographs of normal knee in 30° flexion. [1] They concluded that length of ligamentum patellae and diagonal length of patella bears a ratio of 1. Though the 'Insall-Salvati index' was initially based on radiological findings on lateral view of the knee-joint in X-ray films, different studies have been conducted to measure the 'Insall-Salvati index', namely through cadaveric dissection, sagittal MRI

and ultrasonography, keeping the principle of the index constant.

Aims and Objectives

1. To measure patellar height by 'Insall-Salvati ratio' from MRI.
2. To evaluate different physiological factors, e.g., age, sex, side etc affecting 'Insall-Salvati ratio'.

Materials and Methods

After taking approval from institutional ethical committee, the study was conducted in the KPC Medical College and Hospital over 1 year period (1st November, 2021- 31st October, 2022) of time. Detailed history was taken from 93 patients admitted in the Department of Orthopaedics in whom examinations of both the lower limbs were possible irrespective of their chief complaints and clinical features. Patients with splint, compressive bandage, patients who have just undergone bone marrow transplantation from iliac crest were excluded from the study.

186 knee joints, i.e., both knee joints of all the 93 patients were subjected to radiological investigation (MRI). The data obtained by the examination was analysed to see variation of Patellar Height by 'Insall-Salvati ratio' with sex, age and laterality and also to see the distribution of patients with respect of knee pain.

Results

Age and sex distribution of the study population were as follows-

Among 51 females, 27 were above or equal to 20 years and 24 were between 10-19 years (i.e. less than 20 years). Out of 42 male patients the figures were 24 and 18 respectively.

The clinical method which was newly attempted in this study, showed no statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) from their radiological one both on the right and left sides. The scenario was similar for both the age groups and for male as well as female patients.

Figure 1: Comparison of Mean of Insall-Salvati Index between Two Methods of Measurement in Right side

Figure 2: Comparison of Mean of Insall-Salvati Index between Two Methods of Measurement in left side

Discussion

The present study compared “Insall-Salvati index” measured by radiological method (MRI) and clinical method separately in right and left sides independently in male and female in two separate age groups (<20years and equal or > 20 years age group) by paired t-test (In all the separate group) the result showed no significant statistical difference ($p \text{ value} > 0.05$).

In the adolescent age group, especially during growth spurt; stretching of the ligamentum patellae is radiologically proved to be responsible

for patella alta. [2,3,4] The present study, being a cross-sectional one, routine serial roentgenogram could not be employed. But, the study was conducted on $42 \times 2 = 84$ knee joints of subjects aged below 20 years and $51 \times 2 = 102$ knee joints of subjects aged 20 years and above, separately in males and females showed no significant differences both clinically and radiologically.

No statistically significant difference of “Insall-Salvati index” between male and female in both age groups using either methods of measurements could be established in the present study. This is in

accordance to findings of most of the other studies. [5,6,7,8]

Racial variation had been discussed in previous literatures. [9,10] The present study conducted from peoples belonging to several racial groups. No significant difference could be observed.

Conclusion

The clinical method could not yield any significant difference from radiological method within subjects of comparable age groups on either side in either sex. Even, it failed to show any difference between the two age groups referred to in the present study. Comparison between two sex and two sides also could not reveal any significant statistical difference within comparable groups.

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